

CALCULATION OF TRANSIENT STRESSES DURING MOISTURE ABSORPTION AND DESORPTION IN LAMINATED PLATES

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ABSTRACT

The present paper deals with the calculation of transient and non uniform stress fields which are induced by transient moisture concentration distributions in laminated composite plates. It is shown that the heterogeneity and anisotropy of such plates generally result in transient stress distributions which are very different from the equilibrium stress distributions. Some stacking sequences exhibit important stresses within the plies. These stresses have to be taken into account for the design of composite structures submitted to a moist environment.

INTRODUCTION

The experience of these last years, especially in aeronautics, shows the importance of environmental effects on the mechanical properties of composites as well as on their long term behaviour. The most important environmental factors are temperature, humidity and radiations. Among the above phenomena, water diffusion in composites can cause plastification and hydrolyse of the polymeric matrix, and later a possible decohesion of the fibre-matrix interface. As a result, the prediction of the hygrothermal response of composite structures submitted to transient conditions of temperature and moisture must be studied.

The diffusion equations used for the modelling of the absorption phenomenon were obtained using an analogy between heat conduction transfer and mass transfer. However the temperature inside the material reaches equilibrium much faster than the moisture concentration. For example, the ratio between thermal and mass diffusivities is about 10^6 for most materials [1]. So laminates are generally submitted to uniform temperature fields which induce residual thermal stresses which can be computed using the classical laminated plate theory [2]. On the other hand, the water absorption kinetic is very slow, and laminates are therefore often submitted to transient moisture concentrations. Hence, computing hygroscopic stresses at equilibrium does not lead to realistic values of the stresses. Therefore, it is necessary to compute transient hygroscopic

stresses during the diffusion process. To the authors' knowledge, only Hahn and Kim [3] have carried out such a study for three types of laminates.

The aim of this paper is to present a simplified approach to calculate transient hygroscopic stresses within laminated plates. This method is then used to analyse the transient behaviour of different laminates submitted to a humid environment. It is shown that these stresses can be very different from those obtained at equilibrium. For example, unexpected and non negligible stress peaks will be detected for some stacking sequences.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

CALCULATION OF THE MOISTURE CONCENTRATION

Consider a laminated plate of thickness h submitted on the two sides to the same humid environment. The plate is considered to be infinite in x and y directions and the moisture concentration varies only in the z direction. Hence the problem is one dimensional. The moisture concentration within the plate is described by Fick's equation [1]. If the diffusivity D_z is assumed to be constant, this equation reduces to :

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D_z \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

The solution of Eqn (1) with constant boundary conditions is obtained using a serial development for the concentration c [1],[4]. An approximate solution can be obtained using the finite difference method. Any problem with fluctuating boundary conditions can be solved with this approach. In our case, each ply is divided into "subplies", and the actual concentration distribution is approximated by a linear by parts function. Subsequently, stresses and strains are linear by parts and the equations of compatibility will be valid within each "subply".

CALCULATION OF THE NONMECHANICAL STRESSES

The moisture concentration within the laminated plate leads to residual stresses. These stresses will be computed introducing a generalisation of the method given by Tsai [2] for uniform concentration distribution. At a given time t , the moisture concentration is given by the finite difference programme. The first step is to calculate the free expansions e_x and e_y . These strains are calculated at each point z_k through the thickness where the concentration $c(z_k, t)$ has been calculated (see Fig 1). k lies between 0 and N , where N is the product of the number of plies n_p by the number of "subplies" n_s (5 in the present case).

Figure 1. Definition of the different distances involved in the calculation of the residual stresses.

In the ply axes, the free expansions are given by :

$$\begin{aligned} e_x^{(k)} &= \alpha_x \Delta T + \beta_x c(z_k, t) \\ e_y^{(k)} &= \alpha_y \Delta T + \beta_y c(z_k, t) \\ e_s^{(k)} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The nonmechanical stresses $\sigma_i^n^{(k)}$, $i = x, y, s$, are then computed :

$$\sigma_i^n^{(k)} = Q_{ij} e_j^{(k)} \quad (3)$$

In the laminate axes, these stresses become $\sigma_\alpha^n^{(k)}$, $\alpha = 1, 2, 6$. The nonmechanical in-plane stress resultant components N_α^n and moment components M_α^n are given by :

$$N_\alpha^n = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \sigma_\alpha^n dz \quad \text{and} \quad M_\alpha^n = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} z \sigma_\alpha^n dz \quad (4)$$

N_α^n and M_α^n are calculated assuming a linear distribution of the nonmechanical stresses $\sigma_\alpha^n^{(k)}$ between z_k and z_{k+1} , $k = 0..N-1$:

$$z_k < z < z_{k+1} \quad \sigma_\alpha^n^{(k)} = a_\alpha^{(k)} z + b_\alpha^{(k)} \quad (5)$$

where $a_\alpha^{(k)}$ and $b_\alpha^{(k)}$ are deduced from $\sigma_\alpha^n^{(k)}$ and $\sigma_\alpha^n^{(k+1)}$:

$$a_\alpha^{(k)} = \frac{\sigma_\alpha^n^{(k+1)} - \sigma_\alpha^n^{(k)}}{z_{k+1} - z_k} \quad b_\alpha^{(k)} = \sigma_\alpha^n^{(k)} - a_\alpha^{(k)} z_k \quad (6)$$

In this case, Equ (4) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} N_\alpha^n &= \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} a_\alpha^{(k)} \frac{(z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2)}{2} + b_\alpha^{(k)} (z_{k+1} - z_k) \\ M_\alpha^n &= \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} a_\alpha^{(k)} \frac{(z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3)}{3} + b_\alpha^{(k)} \frac{(z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2)}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The nonmechanical strains are computed using the stress-strain relations [2] :

$$\begin{aligned} \{\epsilon^{0n}\} &= [\alpha] \{N^n\} + [\beta] \{M^n\} \\ \{k^n\} &= [\beta]^t \{N^n\} + [\delta] \{M^n\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Then, the nonmechanical strains $\epsilon_\alpha^n^{(k)}$ are computed at each point z_k :

$$\epsilon_\alpha^n^{(k)} = \epsilon_\alpha^{0n} + z_k k_\alpha^n \quad (9)$$

In the ply axes, these strains become $\epsilon_i^{n(k)}$. The residual strains are obtained from the difference between the nonmechanical strains and the free expansions :

$$\epsilon_i^r(k) = \epsilon_i^{n(k)} - \epsilon_i^{(k)} \quad (10)$$

Finally, the residual stresses $\sigma_i^r(k)$ in the ply axes are given by :

$$\sigma_i^r(k) = Q_{ij} \epsilon_j^r(k) \quad (11)$$

RESULTS

PRESENTATION AND VALIDATION OF THE PROGRAMME

The previous method has been programmed. The moisture concentration within the thickness is computed in a first part using the finite difference method. Notice that the calculation stability is fulfilled when the ratio K defined in Eqn (14) is less than 0.5 [5].

$$K = D_z \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta z)^2} \quad (12)$$

where Δt and Δz are the time and the space steps respectively. The concentration is then computed at six points within each ply. To satisfy the condition $K < 0.5$, Δt is such that

$$\Delta t < \frac{0.5 (\Delta z)^2}{D_z} \quad (13)$$

The stiffness and compliance matrices are calculated in a second part. Residual stresses and strains are finally computed in a third part.

The material used for the simulations is a carbon/epoxy composite whose elastic properties are given in Table 1. This material has a very high degree of anisotropy. Consequently, the effect of the transient hygrothermal phenomena will be all the more apparent. For the sake of simplicity, it is assumed that the elastic properties do not vary during the diffusion process. This point is only approximately verified in practice [1],[6].

Table 1. Mechanical properties of material (after [2])

material	E_x GPa	E_y GPa	ν_x -	G_{xy} GPa	α_x $10^{-6} K^{-1}$	α_y $10^{-6} K^{-1}$	β_x -	β_y -
carbon/epoxy	181	10.3	0.28	7.17	0.02	22.5	0	0.6

The moisture diffusion within a laminated plate is described by three parameters. The first one is the diffusivity D_z which depends on both the material and the temperature. The second one is the maximum concentration c_{maxi} which depends on both the material and the fluid (humid air or water). The third one is the time required to reach the equilibrium. This last parameter depends only on the diffusivity and the thickness of the plate. Let $t_{95\%}$ be the time required by the moisture concentration at the middle of the plate to reach 95% of the maximum concentration :

$$c(0, t_{95\%}) = 0.95 c_{\text{ext}} \tag{14}$$

$t_{95\%}$ is computed using the finite difference programme. The three parameters D_z , c_{maxi} and $t_{95\%}$ are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Environmental conditions and diffusion parameters (after [1])

material	temperature °C	relative humidity %	D_z mm ² /s	c_{maxi} %	$t_{95\%}$ hours
carbon/epoxy	20	100	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-8}$	1.5	4222

To start with, the programme has been checked with results obtained in the literature. First, it has been pointed out that the difference between results obtained with the present method and those obtained using a serial development is less than 3.5 %. Then, it has been shown for large values of t that the transient residual stresses actually tend towards the residual stresses computed with a constant moisture concentration within the laminate thickness. Results obtained by Hahn and Kim [3] have also been considered. The calculations have been performed for three different carbon/epoxy laminates : [0]g_T, [0, 90₃]S and [0₄, 90₄]T exposed to a humid environment. It has been checked that the results obtained with the present approach are in agreement with those obtained by Hahn and Kim [3]. Little discrepancies have been observed. They can be due to the analytical model of Hahn and Kim [3] that considers swelling strains to be zero under a threshold of moisture concentration.

ABSORPTION IN A UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATE

The calculations were performed under the following assumptions. The difference ΔT between the room and the stress-free temperatures is $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$. The initial moisture concentration within the laminate is zero. The plate is suddenly submitted to a humid environment characterised by a maximal concentration c_{maxi} given in Table 2. Stresses σ_x^r and σ_y^r are depicted in Fig 2, 3.

Figure 2. Residual longitudinal stress σ_x^r through the thickness of a carbon/epoxy unidirectional laminate. — INI, —□— $0.1 t_{95\%}$, —△— $t_{95\%}$.

Figure 3. Residual transverse stress σ_y^r through the thickness of a carbon/epoxy unidirectional laminate. ——— INI, —□— 0.1 $t_{95\%}$, —△— $t_{95\%}$.

Owing to the symmetry of the present problem, the shear stress σ_s^r is zero in the ply axes. Four curves are particularly emphasized in all figures of the present paper : the stress distribution in the initial state (INI), the stress distribution obtained when the moisture saturation is achieved (SAT), the stress distributions at $t = t_{95\%}$ and $t = t_{95\%}/10$. In the case of a unidirectional laminate, the first two distributions are zero. The time interval between the different curves is one tenth of $t_{95\%}$. Some relevant points appear clearly. The external plies are subjected to compressive stresses while the internal plies are subjected to tensile stresses during the absorption process. There are two points where the stress is zero between $0.1t_{95\%}$ and $t_{95\%}$. They are located approximately at about one fourth of the thickness from the external plate faces. The maximum value of the stress σ_x^r is negligible compared to both the longitudinal tensile and compressive strengths X and X' reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Strength data of the material used for simulations (after [2])

material	X GPa	X' GPa	Y GPa	Y' GPa	S GPa
carbon/epoxy	1500	1500	40	246	68

The transverse residual stress σ_y^r is not negligible compared to both the transverse tensile and compressive strengths Y and Y'. Indeed, the maximum value of σ_y^r reaches 75% of the tensile strength Y at the beginning of the absorption process. A more refined study presented shows that this maximum value of σ_y^r is not greater at the early steps of the absorption [7].

ABSORPTION IN ANGLE-PLY LAMINATES [+θ, -θ]_{2S}

This study concerns angle-ply laminates [+θ, -θ]_{2S}, with θ = 10, 20, 30, 45 degrees. In all cases, the longitudinal residual stress σ_x^r is negligible compared to longitudinal strengths X and X'. Except in the case θ = 45°, the residual shear stress is different from zero. This value increases regularly from zero to the value at equilibrium. In all cases, no shear stress peaks have been

observed. The maximum stress is obtained for $\theta=20^\circ$ and is equal to 28 MPa. This last value is about 42% of the shear strength S given in Table 3. It is to be noticed that the shear stress remains constant within each ply at any time. This property has been observed for all studied laminates. This is due to the fact that residual strains are defined as the difference between the nonmechanical strains and the free expansions (Eqn (12)). The nonmechanical strains are uniform within each ply for symmetric boundary conditions and uncoupled laminates. The free shear expansion is equal to zero (Eqn (4)). As a result, the residual shear stresses and strains are uniform within each ply.

The transverse stress σ_y^r is plotted in Fig 4 for $\theta = 45^\circ$. As in the case of a unidirectional laminate, the external plies are submitted to transverse compressive stresses during the absorption procedure. It clearly appears that transverse compressive and tensile stress peaks arise within middle and external plies. These stress peaks can be defined as the difference between the transient stresses and the initial or equilibrium stresses. These peaks reach their maximum at the beginning of the absorption process. However, they decrease when θ increases and reach about zero when $\theta = 45^\circ$. In this case, σ_y^r decreases regularly. In all cases, the maximum value of this tensile stress cannot be neglected compared to the transverse tensile strength Y .

Figure 4. Residual transverse stress σ_y^r through the thickness of a carbon/epoxy laminate $[+45, -45]_{2S}$ during absorption. — INI, —□— $0.1 t_{95\%}$, —△— $t_{95\%}$, - - - SAT.

DESORPTION IN ANGLE-PLY LAMINATES $[+\theta, -\theta]_{2S}$

The initial concentration within the laminate is assumed to be equal to c_{maxi} given in Table 2 and it is suddenly exposed to dry air. The results obtained in the case $\theta = 45^\circ$ are plotted in Fig. 4. The curves are symmetrical compared to those obtained for the absorption (Fig 4). The external plies are subjected to tensile stresses. A more precise study shows that the value of this stress reaches 89 MPa in the external plies at the beginning of the desorption. This value is twice the transverse tensile strength Y and failure should appear. However, it must be pointed out that this calculation does not take into account the variation of elasticity modulus due to the humidity, which is likely to cause a stress relaxation.

Figure 5. Residual transverse stress σ_y^r through the thickness of a carbon/epoxy laminate $[+45, -45]_{2S}$ during desorption. — INI, —□— 0.1 $t_{95\%}$, —△— $t_{95\%}$, - - - SAT.

It should be noted that other stacking sequences as quasi-isotropic or cross-ply laminates have been studied. A particular study concerning the effects of the hygrothermal conditioning of specimens has also been performed [7]. The results are in agreement with the above.

CONCLUSION

Large stress peaks can occur during moisture absorption in laminates depending on the stacking sequence. In particular, conditioning can cause such peaks. The present simplified approach could be extended to advanced mechanical behaviours including the influence of moisture and creep on the stiffnesses. Cyclic environmental conditions could also easily be included.

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